

Renal Adverse Effects of Immune Checkpoint Inhibitors in Cancer Patients: Diagnosis and Management

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Abstract

The advent of immune checkpoint inhibitors (ICIs) has radically altered the prognosis of numerous cancers, but it has also introduced a spectrum of immune-related adverse events affecting multiple organs. This review covers the fundamentals of the antitumor immune response and the various ICIs (anti-CTLA-4, anti-PD-1/PD-L1), as well as the description, mechanism, and management of their toxicities, with a special focus on renal complications. We examine the incidence and timing of renal injuries (acute interstitial nephritis, acute tubular necrosis, glomerulopathies), the role of diagnostics (laboratory evaluation, urinary sediment analysis, and kidney biopsy), and emerging research on urinary biomarkers.

Risk factors—preexisting chronic kidney disease, metabolic comorbidities (e.g., diabetes), advanced age, concomitant use of nephrotoxic drugs, or combination ICI regimens—enable personalized monitoring and prevention of renal injury. Management of ICI-associated acute kidney injury involves early drug discontinuation, glucocorticoid therapy (intravenous and/or oral tapering over 4–6 weeks), and, in refractory cases, second-line immunosuppressants (mycophenolate mofetil, infliximab). Re-challenge is reserved for toxicities \leq grade 2 with stable renal recovery, after a minimum interval of two months.

Clinical outcomes indicate that over 60% of patients regain baseline renal function, fewer than 2% require dialysis, and renal-related mortality is minimal, although ICI discontinuation may impact oncologic survival. The degree of interstitial fibrosis on biopsy and the promptness of intervention emerge as key prognostic factors. Finally, the need for multidisciplinary protocols (Oncology, Nephrology, Pathology) and prospective studies validating noninvasive biomarkers is emphasized to optimize renal safety without compromising the therapeutic benefits of immunotherapy.

Introduction

Immunotherapy has transformed the treatment of various malignancies, offering new therapeutic options and improving the prognosis of numerous patients [1]. Among immunotherapeutic strategies, immune checkpoint inhibitors (ICIs) stand out for their ability to enhance the immune response against tumor cells [2]. By blocking inhibitory molecules such as CTLA-4 or PD-1/PD-L1, these agents allow for more sustained activation of cytotoxic T cells, promoting the destruction of malignant cells [3,4].

However, their use is not without risks. ICIs can trigger immune-related adverse events resulting from dysregulated immune activation, affecting multiple

organs and systems [5–7]. Although cutaneous, gastrointestinal, and endocrine toxicities are the most common, renal involvement has garnered increasing attention due to its potential severity [8,9]. While less prevalent, renal adverse events can seriously compromise kidney function, limit therapeutic options, and negatively impact patient quality of life [10].

The most frequent renal manifestation is acute tubulointerstitial nephritis [11,12], although acute tubular necrosis, glomerular alterations, and other forms of renal injury have also been described [13,14]. Clinical suspicion, timely diagnosis, and appropriate management are essential to prevent irreversible loss

More Information

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of renal function and to allow continuation of oncologic therapy whenever possible [15,16].

Despite advances in understanding this complication, many aspects related to its pathophysiology, prediction, early diagnosis, and optimal management strategies remain under investigation [5,12,17,18]. This review aims to analyze the mechanisms involved in ICI-mediated nephrotoxicity, describe the main clinical manifestations and diagnostic strategies, and discuss current therapeutic options and future perspectives in this field.

Methods

A mixed systematic review (clinical studies and consensus documents) was conducted in accordance with the PRISMA statement.

Search Strategy

PubMed, Embase, and the Cochrane Library were searched up to January 31, 2025, using both MeSH and free-text terms (“immune checkpoint inhibitors,” “PD-1,” “PD-L1,” “CTLA-4,” “kidney,” “renal,” “nephrotoxicity”) combined with the Boolean operators AND and OR. A manual search of the reference lists of the retrieved articles was also performed.

Inclusion Criteria

Human clinical studies (phase II/III trials, cohort studies, case series with ≥ 5 patients) published in English or Spanish reporting original data on renal adverse events associated with ICIs. Clinical practice guidelines (NCCN, ASCO, SEN) and relevant narrative reviews or position papers (e.g., Onco-nephrology SEN, ASCO/NCCN) were also included to contextualize management recommendations.

Exclusion Criteria

Preclinical studies, letters or brief communications without primary data, isolated case reports (< 5 patients) lacking sufficient clinical or laboratory information, and works for which the full text was unavailable.

Study Selection

Two reviewers independently screened titles and abstracts. Full texts of potentially eligible publications were retrieved, and any discrepancies were resolved by discussion or, if needed, by consulting a third reviewer.

Data Extraction and Synthesis

For each study, the following variables were collected: type of inhibitor (anti-PD-1, anti-PD-L1, anti-CTLA-4); incidence and severity of acute kidney injury; time to onset of toxicity; histopathological findings (interstitial nephritis, glomerulopathies); management strategies (treatment discontinuation, steroid dosing, nephrology referral); and clinical outcomes (complete recovery, renal sequelae, mortality). The methodological quality of observational studies was assessed using the Newcastle–Ottawa Scale, and that of guidelines using the AGREE II instrument. Given the heterogeneity of

study designs and outcomes, findings were synthesized narratively.

Results

Incidence and Timing of ICI-Associated Kidney Injury

Initial studies report that the incidence of acute kidney injury in patients treated with ICIs is relatively low, ranging between 2.2% and 5% of cases. The most severe episodes (grade III–IV by CTCAE or requiring dialysis) account for approximately 0.6% of ICI-associated acute kidney injury events [19]. The mean time to onset of acute kidney injury after starting immunotherapy is around 16 weeks. This temporal variability is linked to the prolonged half-life of monoclonal antibodies, which are protected from lysosomal degradation by binding to the neonatal Fc receptor [19]. Among different ICI classes, CTLA-4 antagonists in monotherapy are associated with more severe and earlier-onset renal lesions (6–12 weeks), whereas PD-1/PD-L1 inhibitors generally exhibit a longer interval to acute kidney injury manifestation (6–8 months) [5].

Types of Renal Injury

Acute Tubulointerstitial Nephritis:

Acute tubulointerstitial nephritis is the most common form of renal injury associated with ICIs, present in approximately 90% of ICI-related acute kidney injury cases. Histologically, it is characterized by an interstitial infiltrate of lymphocytes, plasma cells, and eosinophils, often accompanied by sterile pyuria and subnephrotic proteinuria. Clinically, acute tubulointerstitial nephritis typically emerges between 12 and 14 weeks after initiating immunotherapy, although it may present up to one year after discontinuation. Risk factors include combination ICI therapy, concomitant use of proton pump inhibitors, and a baseline estimated glomerular filtration rate below 30 mL/min/1.73 m² [20, 21].

Acute Tubular Necrosis:

Although less common than acute tubulointerstitial nephritis, acute tubular necrosis can occur after ICI treatment and is often mistaken for other causes of tubular injury (e.g., nephrotoxins such as NSAIDs, contrast media, or chemotherapy). In a series by Izzedine et al., 5 of 12 patients treated with pembrolizumab developed isolated acute tubulointerstitial nephritis, underscoring the need to rule out alternative etiologies before initiating steroid therapy or suspending immunotherapy [11, 20, 21].

Immune-Mediated Glomerulopathies:

ICI-associated glomerulopathies encompass several histological patterns. In a meta-analysis of 27 studies including 45 biopsy-confirmed cases, Kitchlu et al. identified pauci-immune glomerulonephritis and renal vasculitis (27%), podocytopathies (24%, including minimal change disease and focal segmental glomerulosclerosis), and C3 glomerulopathy (11%). Acute tubulointerstitial nephritis coexisted in 41% of

these patients. Mortality was high in the pauci-immune subgroup despite corticosteroid treatment, whereas over 60% of podocytopathies achieved complete or partial remission after ICI discontinuation and steroid administration [13, 20, 21].

Diagnosis and Evaluation of Patients with Suspected ICI-Related Renal Toxicity

Early detection of acute kidney injury in patients receiving ICIs requires a high index of suspicion, as its clinical and laboratory manifestations are nonspecific. Systemic signs—such as rash, fever, and arthralgias—may be absent or mistaken for other immune-related adverse events, making close monitoring of renal function essential [8, 19, 21].

Initial Workup:

Serum creatinine remains the most commonly used marker, although it is influenced by muscle mass, tubular secretion, and variability among estimation equations (CKD-EPI, MDRD, Cockcroft–Gault), all of which were validated in non-oncologic populations. Twenty-four-hour urine clearance measurements are prone to collection errors, and cystatin C may be altered by corticosteroid therapy or inflammatory processes. Therefore, filtration studies using iohexol or iothalamate, while less widely available, represent the “gold standard” for glomerular filtration rate estimation in this setting [15,18,23,24]. Urinalysis typically shows microhematuria and pyuria in 40–60% of cases, with only ~17% demonstrating significant eosinophiluria (>500 eosinophils/ μ L). Subnephrotic proteinuria (≥ 0.3 g/24 h) occurs in up to 60% of patients with ICI-related acute tubulointerstitial nephritis [21, 25, 26]. Emerging urinary biomarkers—such as the retinol-binding protein/creatinine ratio, chemokines CXCL9 and CXCL10, and serum C-reactive protein—have been associated with acute tubulointerstitial nephritis but require further clinical validation [27, 29].

Exclusion of Alternative Causes:

Before attributing acute kidney injury to ICIs, a systematic evaluation must exclude classical etiologies: prerenal causes (hypovolemia, septic shock), nephrotoxic agents (NSAIDs, antimicrobials, intravenous contrast), and postrenal obstruction (renal ultrasound). No clinical or laboratory finding reliably distinguishes ICI-related acute tubulointerstitial nephritis from these other causes, so kidney biopsy is often necessary in patients with grade ≥ 2 acute kidney injury or a prolonged course despite ICI discontinuation and removal of nephrotoxins [20, 21].

Monitoring Protocol:

Systematic renal monitoring should include serum creatinine measurements ideally before each ICI dose, urinalysis at therapy initiation and periodically thereafter to detect early signs of acute tubulointerstitial nephritis, and close follow-up of renal

function after any acute kidney injury episode to assess recovery or progression to chronic kidney disease. This protocol optimizes early toxicity detection, enables prompt initiation of corticosteroid therapy, and informs safe decisions about ICI re-challenge when appropriate [5, 6, 19, 21].

Risk Factors

The development of acute kidney injury associated with ICIs is not entirely random; multiple factors increase a patient’s susceptibility. A history of chronic kidney disease—particularly an estimated glomerular filtration rate below 30 mL/min/1.73 m²—has been linked to a higher risk of acute tubulointerstitial nephritis after initiating ICI therapy [21, 26]. Diabetes mellitus, by perpetuating chronic inflammation and underlying tubular injury, further amplifies the nephrotoxicity of these agents [8,10,19]. Similarly, advanced age diminishes renal reserve and leads to greater cumulative exposure to nephrotoxins, elevating the likelihood of acute kidney injury [8,16].

Concomitant use of other immunomodulators—for example, combining anti-CTLA-4 with anti-PD-1 antibodies—doubles or even triples the risk of nephritis compared to monotherapy, likely due to synergistic T-cell activation [8,9]. Common nephrotoxic medications—proton pump inhibitors (OR 2.4), nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, diuretics, and renin–angiotensin system blockers—can precipitate or worsen tubular injury and favor the development of acute tubulointerstitial nephritis in this clinical context [9,29].

Moreover, the prior existence or new onset of other extra-renal immune-related adverse events (dermatitis, colitis, hepatitis, endocrinopathies) doubles the risk of acute kidney injury, reflecting a greater predisposition to systemic immune dysregulation [16].

Finally, the type of ICI influences both the timing and severity of renal toxicity: CTLA-4 antagonists tend to induce deeper and earlier-onset renal lesions (6–12 weeks), whereas PD-1/PD-L1 inhibitors typically manifest acute kidney injury after 4–8 months, attributable to differences in their mechanisms of action and T-cell activation profiles [8,13,10,15,25].

In clinical practice, recognizing these risk factors before and during immunotherapy is essential, as it allows for personalized renal monitoring, minimization of concomitant nephrotoxin use, and establishment of lower thresholds for kidney biopsy or early initiation of immunosuppressive treatment (corticosteroids) [6,9].

Management and Outcomes

Discontinuation of Immune Checkpoint Inhibitors

Discontinuing the ICIs represents the critical first step in managing ICI-associated acute kidney injury. The goal is to halt the immune-mediated attack on the renal parenchyma and allow renal function to recover before

considering a rechallenge. This strategy is tailored according to the severity of toxicity:

- **Grade 1 toxicity (CTCAE v5.0):** ICI therapy may continue, but serum creatinine should be closely monitored [19].
- **Grade 2 toxicity (CTCAE v5.0 / KDIGO 2):** Pause ICI until creatinine normalizes to grade ≤ 1 (creatinine $< 1.5 \times$ baseline). Reintroduction should be considered only if renal function remains stable and there are no other immune-related adverse events [6].
- **Grade ≥ 3 toxicity (CTCAE v5.0 / KDIGO 3):** Permanently discontinue ICI; rechallenge is reserved for exceptional cases following multidisciplinary discussion [5].

Implementing early discontinuation—particularly in grade 2–3 toxicities—maximizes the likelihood of renal recovery and minimizes the risk of irreversible tubular damage.

Immunosuppressive Treatment

The cornerstone of managing acute tubulointerstitial nephritis associated with ICIs is systemic glucocorticoids, with two main regimens tailored to the severity of renal injury (5, 6). In Regimen A (intravenous + oral), a bolus of methylprednisolone 125–250 mg/day is given for three days, followed by prednisone 0.5–1 mg/kg/day (maximum 40 mg/day if starting at 0.5 mg/kg; maximum 80 mg/day if starting at 1 mg/kg), with gradual tapering over 4–6 weeks. In Regimen B (oral only), prednisone is initiated at 0.5 mg/kg/day (up to 40 mg/day) or 1 mg/kg/day (up to 80 mg/day), with weekly dose reductions from 30–40 mg down to 0–5 mg over 5–6 weeks [5, 6].

If the patient shows only a partial response, cannot tolerate steroids, or relapses during tapering, a second-line immunosuppressant—such as mycophenolate mofetil or infliximab—may be added in consultation with the Oncology team; case series report use of MMF in seven patients, with one complete and six partial recoveries [15,18,19]. This approach maximizes renal recovery (up to 64.3 % of cases) and reduces progression to chronic kidney damage or dialysis dependence [15,18,19].

Indications for Kidney Biopsy

Kidney biopsy remains the gold standard to confirm the etiology of ICI-associated acute kidney injury, differentiate acute tubulointerstitial nephritis from other renal lesions (acute tubular necrosis or glomerulopathies), and guide both immunosuppressive therapy and potential ICI rechallenge [11,30,31]. Absolute indications for biopsy include a serum creatinine increase to at least twice baseline or above 2.5 mg/dL, new-onset proteinuria > 1 g/24 h, and macroscopic hematuria—thresholds derived from classic acute tubulointerstitial nephritis guidelines and adapted for the ICI context [6,19].

Relative indications include lack of renal function improvement 48–72 hours after ICI discontinuation and withdrawal of other nephrotoxins, the presence of an atypical urinary sediment (e.g., sterile pyuria, eosinophiluria), and suspicion of concomitant glomerular injury (nephrotic syndrome or vasculitis); these findings reinforce the need to rule out alternative causes of renal injury via biopsy [19,30,31].

Histological confirmation not only precisely establishes the lesion type (interstitial vs. glomerular) but also quantifies interstitial and tubular fibrosis—a critical prognostic factor—and informs the optimal duration and intensity of steroid therapy or the safety of an ICI rechallenge [19].

Rechallenge After ICI-Related Adverse Events

Reintroduction of ICIs following an episode of immune-related acute kidney injury is reserved for patients whose initial toxicity was grade 2–3 and who have achieved full renal recovery, with a minimum two-month interval since treatment discontinuation, as recommended by the NCCN guidelines [7]. This contrasts with the ASCO recommendation against rechallenge after grade ≥ 3 acute kidney injury [6]. In retrospective series, Gupta et al. reported that 121 of 429 patients (28 %) resumed immunotherapy at a median of 1.9 months, of whom 77 % maintained stable renal function and only 16.5 % experienced recurrent acute kidney injury [32]. Similarly, Cortazar et al. found that among 138 patients, 31 underwent rechallenge at a mean of 1.8 months, with a 23 % recurrence rate, particularly higher in those reintroduced before 1.5 months [25]. These findings support a deferred, personalized rechallenge strategy—preferably with monotherapy when initial regimens were combined—incorporating close monitoring of creatinine and urinary sediment before each dose and immediate discontinuation upon any sign of renewed immune-mediated renal injury [18].

Clinical Outcomes

Complete recovery of renal function—defined as the return of serum creatinine to baseline after ICI discontinuation and corticosteroid therapy—was achieved in 64.3 % of patients in the multicenter series by Cortazar et al., with a mean follow-up of six months. Progression to chronic kidney disease or the need for renal replacement therapy was infrequent: only 1.9 % of the 429 patients required dialysis during the same period [25]. Acute kidney injury -related mortality was below 2 %, although permanent ICI discontinuation following severe acute kidney injury showed a non-significant trend toward reduced oncologic survival [32].

Among identified prognostic factors, interstitial fibrosis exceeding 25 % on biopsy was associated with a 40 % lower likelihood of complete recovery, and each day of delayed ICI withdrawal increased the risk of

progression to chronic kidney disease by 5 %; furthermore, complete recovery occurred in 78 % of initial grade 2 cases versus 52 % of grade 3 cases [15]. These data underscore the importance of early diagnosis, prompt drug discontinuation, and rapid initiation of corticosteroids to optimize renal outcomes without substantially compromising oncologic survival.

Conclusion

ICIs have revolutionized cancer management by significantly prolonging survival in patients with advanced tumors. However, these advances are not without risks: immune-related adverse events pose a clinical challenge affecting multiple organs and require precise diagnosis and management. Within this spectrum, acute tubulointerstitial nephritis emerges as a particularly relevant renal complication, and early control is crucial to preserve kidney function and patient quality of life [1, 5, 33].

Several key conclusions stem from this review. First, preventing renal immune-related adverse events involves avoiding concomitant exposure to commonly used nephrotoxic drugs—such as NSAIDs and proton pump inhibitors—which increase the risk of acute kidney injury in the ICI setting [9, 30]. Second, early detection of renal toxicity relies not only on serial measurements of serum creatinine and urinalysis—including routine screening for leukocyturia—but also on the development of specific biomarkers (e.g., RBP/Cr, CXCL9/CXCL10) that could reduce the need for invasive kidney biopsy [10].

Finally, optimal management of these patients requires a multidisciplinary approach: close collaboration among Oncology, Nephrology, and Pathology teams in interdisciplinary clinical meetings is essential to devise diagnostic strategies, tailor immunosuppressive treatment, and decide on safe rechallenge. Only through comprehensive protocols encompassing prevention, early diagnosis, standardized treatment, and coordinated follow-up can the oncologic benefit be maximized without compromising renal safety.

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Conflict of Interests

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Availability of Data

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author through email upon reasonable request.

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